

ISic3395

I.Sicily inscription 3395

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

limestone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2015.11.13 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Soluntum

Place of origin (modern)

Solunto

Provenance

agora

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Solunto, Area Archeologica e
Antiquarium di Solunto

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR137130

1. [--- ἐποί]ησε

2. [--- Ἀ]τεμιδω [ρ ? ---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645613

EDR 137130

Bibliography

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graecum. At 58.1055.4

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Portale, E.C. 2006. Problemi dell'archeologia della Sicilia ellenistico-romana: il caso di Solunto. *Archeologia Classica*. 57: 49-114. At 93 n.80

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